

REPAIR OF TYPE B DAMAGE TO MARINE SANDWICH STRUCTURES

Rodney S. Thomson¹, Raoul E. Luescher¹, Ivan Grabovac²

¹ *Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Limited,
506 Lorimer Street, Fishermens Bend, Victoria, 3207, Australia.*

² *Department of Defence, DSTO, Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory,
PO Box 4331 Melbourne, Victoria, 3001, Australia.*

SUMMARY: Marine vessels manufactured from sandwich structures with glass reinforced polymer (GRP) composite skins and PVC core are now common. These vessels will inevitably be subjected to damage and the approach used in carrying out the repair is critical to maintain the strength and stiffness of the structure. This paper concerns the repair of Type B damage to sandwich structures, defined as damage to one skin and the core. The Royal Australian Navy (RAN) repair technique was evaluated and found to be difficult to carry out and could result in a poor quality repair. Static flexural testing indicated that the presence of voids in the bondline seriously affected the strength of the repair. A modified repair technique was proposed to simplify several aspects of the repair procedure and to improve the repair quality. Test results showed that the modified repair technique overcame the problems associated with the RAN technique.

KEYWORDS: sandwich structures, repair, marine structures

INTRODUCTION

Glass reinforced polymer (GRP) composites are being used increasingly in the maritime industry for the manufacture of hulls, superstructures and fittings. In Australia, the Bay class Inshore Minehunters were manufactured entirely from GRP sandwich construction [1]. The Huon Class Coastal Minehunters are also being manufactured from GRP, but use a monolithic construction technique. Fairings on the Collins class submarines are also manufactured from GRP. In addition to this, GRP finds extensive uses in the civil maritime industry. These structures will inevitably be subjected to damage and effective repair methods must be developed.

Sandwich panels consist of two high strength and stiffness skins separated by a low density, lower strength and stiffness core. Such structures can be subjected to three damage scenarios. The damage can be limited to one skin (Type A), to one skin and the core (Type B), or to both skins and the core (Type C). This paper details an investigation into the repair of Type B damage to GRP/PVC foam sandwich structures representative of the Bay Class minehunters. Type B damage can involve delamination and cracking of the skin, skin to core debonding, and crushing or shear cracking of the core. The approach used in carrying out the repair is critical to maintain the strength and stiffness of the structure. However, the performance of a repair technique must be judged both on its ability to restore the mechanical properties and on the ease of carrying it out.

Various approaches for the repair of such damage have been proposed including those for the United States Coast Guard [2] and the Swedish Mine Counter Measure Vessels [3]. In this research, the technique used by the Royal Australian Navy (RAN) for the repair of Type B damage to the Bay class minehunters was first evaluated. A modified method which simplified the repair procedure while improving the quality was then evaluated. The mechanical performance of the repairs was evaluated by testing specimens under four-point bending.

REPAIR TECHNIQUES FOR “TYPE B” DAMAGE

RAN Technique Description

The RAN repair procedure for Type B damage to GRP/foam sandwich structures of the Bay class minehunters [4] is shown schematically in Fig. 1. The skins of the Bay class minehunters are laminated from alternating plies of 300 g/m² chopped strand mat (CSM) and 600 g/m² woven rovings (WR). A set of one CSM and one WR ply is defined as a layer. The RAN repair procedure is performed in the sequence:

1. *Remove damaged material:* Remove the damaged skin, working from the centre of the damaged region outwards until sound material is encountered. Remove the exposed damaged core leaving the other skin intact.

Fig. 1: RAN repair method for Type B damage to GRP/foam sandwich structures.

2. *Prepare the area for repair:* Prepare the foam core to an angle of 45°. Sand the edge of the laminate to a taper of 20 mm per layer which provides a scarf angle of approximately 6°.
3. *Install the replacement foam:* Use the appropriate grade of foam. Use the minimum amount of adhesive designed for bonding PVC foam (bondline thickness 3 mm maximum). No voids should exist between the undamaged skin and the replacement foam.

4. *Replace the skin:* Use the same number of layers as the original skin. Each successive layer is to be 40 mm longer and wider than the previous layer. Apply one extra layer of GRP extending 100 mm beyond the extent of all damage.

Modified Repair Technique Description

Modifications to the repair technique were based on conclusions drawn from the manufacture and testing of the RAN repair technique. These focussed on ensuring a good quality bondline between the skin and replacement core while simplifying the repair preparation. This was achieved by replacing the 45° bevelled edge on the foam with a 90° bevel. Additionally, the replacement foam core used was in one piece wherever practical. Holes drilled through the replacement core were used to prevent air entrapment as the core was positioned. The repair was also placed under vacuum while the core was being bonded in place to ensure a uniform, thin, high quality bondline. The modified Type B repair method, shown in Fig. 2, is detailed below:

1. *Remove damaged material:* Remove the damaged skin, working from the centre of the damaged region outwards until sound material is encountered. Remove the exposed damaged core leaving the other skin intact.

Fig. 2: Modified repair method for Type B damage to GRP/foam sandwich structures.

2. *Prepare the area for repair:* Prepare the foam core to an angle of 90°. Sand the edge of the laminate to a taper of 20 mm per layer.
3. *Install replacement foam:* Cut out a piece of the appropriate grade foam allowing 1 mm all round for the bondline. Drill 3 mm diameter holes through the core at approximately 100 mm centres. Apply an adhesive designed to be used with PVC foam to the existing skin and core. Carefully place the replacement core, forcing it down lightly to remove entrapped air.

4. *Vacuum bag the core:* Apply a layer of perforated release film and breather over the repair area. Position the vacuum bag over the repair area, sealing it to the surrounding structure. Apply vacuum (20 inHg) until the adhesive has cured. Clean up the area for laminating.
5. *Replace the skin:* Use the same number of layers as in the original skin, keeping the orientations the same also. Each successive layer is to be 40 mm longer and wider than the previous layer. Apply one extra layer of GRP extending 100 mm beyond the extent of all damage.

FOUR-POINT BEND TESTS

Test Methodology

The four-point bend test, as specified in ASTM C-393 [5], was selected to evaluate the mechanical performance of the repair. This test places the core under shear and will thereby identify deficiencies in the core itself or the bond between the replacement core and existing core or skin. While the skins do carry the bending loads under four-point bending, these were not anticipated to be high enough to cause skin failure. Two spans between the outer supports were used; 300 mm and 400 mm. The tests were conducted with the repair facing up (normal position) or facing down (inverted position) which placed the repaired skin under compression or tension respectively. The location of the end of the repair was midway between the outer supports where constant shear stress was carried by the core. The tests were carried out using a four-point bend rig mounted in a Riehle 300 kN testing machine. The tests were conducted in displacement control at a rate of 3 mm per minute. The load, displacement, acoustic emissions, failure load and failure mode were recorded during testing. Except where otherwise stated, six specimens of each repair type, span and position were tested.

Four-Point Bend Specimen Fabrication

A large sandwich panel was first fabricated from which the specimens would be obtained. The skins were fabricated using the hand laminating technique with 300 g/m² CSM, 600 g/m² WR and Derakane 411 vinylester resin. The lay-up of the skins was CSM/WR/CSM giving a nominal thickness of 2.1 mm. The core material was 30 mm thick Divinycell HT90 rigid, crosslinked, PVC foam. Following lamination of both skins, the panel was cut into three sections from which the reference, 300 mm span and 400 mm span specimens were obtained. On two of the sections, the RAN repair for Type B damage was performed as detailed previously. Divilette polyester based thixotropic adhesive was used to bond the replacement core. Since the skins were relatively thin, one ply of CSM was applied over the repair instead of one extra layer. Following complete cure of the panels, 40 mm wide four-point bend specimens were cut.

The same approach and materials were used in the fabrication of the modified repair technique specimens. Again, one ply of CSM was applied over the repair instead of one extra layer.

Reference Specimen Test Results

Reference specimens obtained from the RAN and modified repair panels were tested independently under four-point bending. A total of eight 300 mm span specimens were tested and exhibited consistent load-displacement behaviour. All specimens failed through local skin wrinkling/core crushing under the loading points. This failure mode was characterised by the

load reaching a plateau then slowly dropping as compressive failure of the skin occurred under bending. A large drop in load then occurred associated with tension failure of the same skin. Six 400 mm span reference specimens were tested and behaved consistently although one specimen failed through core shear. The reference specimens from the modified repair panel exhibited slightly lower load carrying capability, as summarised in Table 1. This was the result of minor differences in materials and manufacturing between the two panels.

RAN Repair Test Results

The fabrication quality of the RAN repaired specimens was variable, with a number of defects observed in the bondline between the existing skin and replacement core as well as in the 45° join in the core. Some defects represented 50% of the bondline area. The average strength of the 300 mm span repaired specimens tested in the normal position was 14% lower than the reference specimens, as summarised in Table 1. All specimens failed through core shear and a typical failure is shown in Fig. 3. In the inverted position, the average strength was 7% lower but the scatter in results was much higher. This was due to the bondline between the core and the existing skin being positioned on the compression side of the beam making the presence of any defects more critical. The results of such defects are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

Similar behaviour was observed for the 400 mm span specimens. The specimens tested in the normal position exhibited similar average strength to the reference specimens and all failed through core shear. The average strength of those tested in the inverted position were 14% lower with most specimens failing through debonding of the skin. Again, the scatter was high in the inverted position.

The stiffness of the repaired specimens was generally higher than the reference specimens. The repaired specimens tested in the normal position were in the order of 10% stiffer than the reference specimens while those tested in the inverted position were in the order of 20% stiffer. The repaired specimens had an extra ply of CSM in the repaired skin and a thicker bondline which contributed to the bending stiffness.

Table 1: Summary of the average strength of the two repair techniques.

Test Group	300 mm Span		400 mm Span	
	Average Maximum Load (N/mm)	Standard Deviation (N/mm)	Average Maximum Load (N/mm)	Standard Deviation (N/mm)
RAN - Reference	79.6	1.5	75.4	0.6
RAN - Normal	68.3	4.3	75.4	1.3
RAN - Inverted	74.2	20.1	64.5	33.2
Modified - Reference	75.3	5.9	73.2	2.0
Modified - Normal	83.3	1.9	78.0	4.2
Modified - Inverted	81.8	2.2	77.4	1.2

Fig. 3: Typical core shear failure for a RAN repaired specimen in the normal position.

Fig. 4: Failure initiating from a defect in the 45° bondline of a RAN repair tested in the inverted position.

Fig. 5: Debonding failure due to a defect in the replacement core to skin bondline of a RAN repair tested in the inverted position.

Modified Repair Test Results

The fabrication quality of the specimens repaired using the modified technique was very good, although a small number had minor defects in the bondline between the existing and replacement core. The average strength of the 300 mm span repaired specimens tested in the normal and inverted positions was 11% and 9% greater respectively than that of the reference standards. The test results are summarised in Table 1. Similar results were achieved for 400 mm span specimens with the average strength in the normal and inverted positions being 7% and 6% greater respectively than the reference standards. Approximately one third of the specimens failed through skin wrinkling under the loading points while the remainder failed through core shear. No specimens suffered skin debonding failures. Failure initiated from defects in the core to core join in only three of the specimens, as shown in Fig. 6. However, these specimens did not suffer a significant reduction in failure load.

The stiffness of specimens repaired using the modified technique was approximately 8% greater than the reference specimens in both the normal and inverted positions.

DISCUSSION

The RAN repair technique proved difficult to perform, even under laboratory conditions. The major difficulty was associated with finishing the core to a 45° angle. The angle needed to be accurately maintained to ensure good fit of the replacement core and a consistently even, thin bondline. Under field conditions, preparing the repair area would be more difficult with the use of hand held tools. Additionally, typical repairs would be elliptical in shape. The modified repair technique eliminated the 45° join, which made the repair preparation very straightforward. Drilling holes through the core successfully prevented air entrapment. The use of vacuum when bonding the core into position did increase the complexity of the repair. However, the results indicate that this additional process is justified in achieving excellent repair quality and low scatter in the repaired strength and stiffness. Most facilities where such repairs would be carried out would have access to the required vacuum equipment.

Generally, if the bondline were defect free, the strength of the repaired specimens exceeded that of the reference specimens due primarily to the influence of the extra layer laminated into the repaired skin. However, the presence of defects seriously reduced the strength of the sandwich structure, especially when the affected bondline was under compressive loading.

Fig. 6: Failure of a modified repair specimen from a defect in the bondline.

Compressive loading made the presence of defects more critical as they tended to open up, buckle and grow. In the RAN repaired specimens, defects were noted in the bondline between the existing skin and replacement core as well as in the 45° join between the foam. These voids were the result of air entrapment as the replacement core was positioned. Both cases were subjected to compressive loading under four-point bending in the inverted position.

The average strengths under four-point bending of the specimens repaired using the RAN technique were significantly lower than the reference specimens. Also, the standard deviations of the specimens tested in the inverted position were unacceptably high. This was due primarily to the presence of defects in the bondline formed during the repair process. During testing, debonding and local buckling of the skin occurred when these defects were under compressive loading. Once the skin separated from the core, it carried very little of the bending loads rendering the sandwich structure ineffective. Voids in the bondline between the existing and replacement core also affected the ability of the core to effectively carry shear stress. It was imperative that all bondlines be free of defects to produce an effective repair.

On the other hand, the average strengths of the modified repair specimens were greater than the reference specimens due to the low incidence of defects in the bondline. Some small defects were present in the 90° core join, but were found to be less critical than equivalent defects in the RAN repair technique. This was due to the join in the modified repair technique not being aligned with the direction of the shear stress in the core.

The stiffness of the modified repair technique was slightly lower than the RAN technique, but both were significantly higher than the reference standards. This could lead to the presence of a “hard spot” in the structure resulting from the repair which, in a stiffness critical area, could lead to load redistribution or the potential for failure at the edge of the repair.

CONCLUSIONS

The current recommended RAN technique for the repair of Type B damage to GRP/foam sandwich structures was evaluated and two main deficiencies identified. The first concerned the bevelling of the foam at a 45° angle which was found to be difficult to maintain resulting in an uneven bondline thickness. The second deficiency concerned the formation of large voids between the replacement core and the existing skin or core. These were the result of air entrapment when the foam was positioned. These voids were found to seriously reduce the strength of the repair when the bondline was under compressive loading. A less critical problem concerned the increased stiffness of the repaired structure which could result in a “hard spot”.

A modified repair technique for Type B damage to GRP/foam sandwich structures has been proposed. This technique simplifies several aspects of the repair procedure as well as improving the repair quality and repeatability. This was achieved using 90° butt joins in the foam core, drilling holes through the replacement foam core and by using vacuum bagging when bonding the foam in place. The averaged strengths of specimens using the modified repair technique were greater than the reference specimens while the averaged stiffness was similar to that of the RAN repair technique. The results from the evaluation indicate that the problems associated with the RAN technique for the repair of Type B damage have largely been solved by the proposed modified repair technique.

REFERENCES

1. Hall, D.J. and Robson, B.L., "A Review of the Design and Materials Evaluation Programme for the GRP/Foam Sandwich Composite Hull of the RAN Minehunter," *Composites*, Vol. 15, No. 4, October 1984, pp 266-276.
2. "Marine Composites: Investigation of Fiberglass Reinforced Plastics in Marine Structures," Eric Greene Associates, Inc., U.S. Department of Commerce, National Technical Information Service, PB91-129270.
3. Sjogren, J., Celsing, C. G., Olsson, K. A., Levan, C. G. and Hellbratt, S. E., "Swedish Development of MCMV-Hull Design and Production," *RINA Symposium, London, June, 1984*.
4. "Bay Class Minehunter Inshore Glass Reinforced Plastic Repair Manual", Defence Instruction (Navy) ABR 5803, Royal Australian Navy, July 1992.
5. ASTM C-393, "Standard Test Method for Flexural Properties of Flat Sandwich Constructions," American Society for Testing and Materials, 1988.